

MUSICAL DIDACTIC GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Annotation. The game is the main activity of preschool children, through which the child is formed as a person. The game determines to what extent the child's future educational, labor activity, attitude towards people are formed. This article covers the importance of musical didactic games in preschool educational organizations in the healthy development of students.

Keywords: amateur, feeling-excitement, physical exercise, emotion, the Goya of the game, games that reflect domestic marriage, ethnographer, art science, philosopher, moral relations.

The game has attracted the attention of educators, psychologists, philosophers, ethnographers, art scientists since ancient times. The game arose as early as the era of the primitive collective system, standing in the life of society after Labor and determining its content. Primitive community tribes reflected in their games hunting, war, farming. For example, the process of rice sprinkling of some tribes of that time was carried out with games in a very large solemnity ate.

In some cases, yesa game occurs through the desire to work. For example, a hunter crawls and slips like an animal in front of him to hunt down Tyulen.

In some cases, the yesa child imitates adult labor before his game, later participating in their labor. The game prepares the younger generation for Labor. Such an understanding of the children's game for the First Time K. D. As described by ushinsky ate. In his works, he writes that the content of children's play is determined by their impressions from life, which affect the formation of their personality.

P this idea. F.Lesgaft also affirms that children reflect in their games the impressions they received from the environment. Such activity is of great importance in the development of the child.

Thus, the unanimity of the social event of the game, the reflection of the surrounding being in the game were proved by advanced scientists and educators through their observation and scientific research.

To the theory of children's play (in the 20s and 30s) E. A. Flerina, E. I. Tikheeva, E. A. Scientists such as Arkin founded; later R. YA. Lextman-Abramovich, F. I. Fradkipa, N. M. For The Most Part, A. P. Usova, D. V. Mendzheritskaya, R. I.

Zhukovskaya, T. A. Markova, S. L. Novosyolova, E. V. The research work of Zvorigina and others was devoted to the development of the topic of children's play.

The history, nature of the children's game, the laws of its development L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leont'ev, D. B. El'kanin, A. V. Psychologists such as Zaporozhets and their successors were reflected in scientific research work. A. V. Zaporozhets emphasizes the need to study the reasons that set it in motion, the laws of development, the peculiarities, content and structure of children's play at different age stages, as a result of monitoring children's play from an early age.

The first stage of the first-year-old children's play activity is an introductory game, it is a thing, an item play activity. Its content is complex and subtle movements in manual work.

The next stage is the game of reflection catch. The sleeve is a high point in the development of the psychological content of this first-year-old children's game. When adults carry out educational and educational work with a certain consistency, children of this age learn the name of things and objects, what they are used for, and begin to apply this new knowledge in their games. The content of the children's game at this age is reflected in the subject activity.

At the end of the first age and in the children's game of the second age' reflection of the plot occurs. The reflection of how to use it with the object in the hands of the child is enough. For example, food is eaten with a spoon, tea is drunk from a bowl, lying on the bed, the Ram is yielded by the "mother", etc. On the basis of this, the first edges of the plot-role-playing game begin to surface.

The next stage is a role-playing game, in which children reflect the adult labor and social relations of people familiar to them.

Scientific representations in the direction of the gradual development of children's play activities made it possible to develop clear systematic recommendations for the guidance of children's play activities in different age groups.

Thus, the role of the game in the pedagogical process of the children's garden is very large, and the game is widely used in the upbringing and education of preschool children. Zero:

— the game is an independent activity of children, in which the child's psyche is manifested;

- the game is a form of Organization of the life of preschool children:

- play is one of the means of raising children in every possible way;

- play is a technique and a way to educate and educate children;

- the game is a means of preparing children for educational activities. Research conducted by well-known pedagogues-scientists

by providing comprehensive guidance to the game, it has shown that children can be influenced by the content, organization, structure of the game, moral attitudes of children, the level of development of children's play.

The children's game is diverse in its content, feature, organization, therefore it is divided into categories as follows:

1. Creative games.
2. Rule games.

Creative games are invented by children themselves. There will be no pre-established rules in it. The rule of the game is set by the children themselves in the process of the game.

Creative games include dramatized games, Construction games, games played with natural materials.

The content and rule of rule games are determined by adults. Rule games include: didactic Games, action games, music games, yermak games.

In the article on education and upbringing of children, the ability of adults to choose a game, to lead it correctly, provides for the successful implementation of the tasks set in the "kid's program". The game is a means of developing and raising children. Psychologists consider the game to be a leading activity in the age of bogcha. Thanks to the game, qualities are formed that stimulate the child's transition to a higher stage of development, which is accompanied by significant changes in his psyche.

In the game, all sides of the child's personality are formed with mutual influence on each other. While observing a playing child, one can find out his interests, his vision of the surroundings, his attitude towards adults and comrades.

To educate some quality in a person, it is necessary to develop other aspects of it. For example, a child's interest in play, content-rich games must be created to develop organizational skills. For the development of children's creative games, in turn will need a well-organized children's team.

The game occupies a large place in the system of raising children from the physical side, in the educational work of bogcha, in the education of moral, labor and aesthetic side.

In the game, the requirements and attitudes inherent in a young organism are satisfied, vital activity increases, cheerfulness, vivacity, cheerfulness are brought up. Therefore, in the system of physical education of children, the game occupies a worthy place. Outstanding educator and doctor E. A. Arkin did not say in vain

that the game is a mental vitamin.

The game is inextricably linked with education and training, with observations from everyday life, has a huge educational and educational value. In creative games, an important cognitive process occurs, which triggers the mental strength of the child, requires the activation of thinking, imagination, attention, memory. The child learns to independently solve issues, comes up with a better and easier way to realize what he thinks, learns to use his knowledge and express it in words.

Interest in finding out what is being reflected in the game wakes up. Often the game serves to give children new knowledge and expand their thinking, knowledge framework. In children, towards an interest in the labor of adults, social life, in the heroic deeds of people, such initial dreams arise in them as a future specialty, imitation of loved ones.

A. V. Zaporozhets talks about the import of the game yekan, the game develops the ability to create a system of generalized typical images of the asking subject and events, which are then changed in different ways. Such a developmental feature of fantasy or figurative thinking for the retire future development of the child is an invalid value, he says.

The creative game cannot be subordinated to narrow didactic goals; with the help of this game, very large educational tasks are solved.

The rule game allows you to regularly train the child's sensory development, thinking and speech, involuntary attention and memory, various movements. Each rule game will be aimed at the general development of the child, turning into a certain didactic goal. It is important that education is in the form of a game yega and corresponds to the age characteristics of the child. An interesting game increases the mental activity of the child, in the game the child can solve a more complex issue compared to the one he is engaged in. This is not to say that education should be completely in the form of a game. Education requires the application of various methods and techniques.

The game is one of the forms of education and only gives a good result when combined with another method, these are observation, conversation, reading, etc. While playing, the child learns to use his knowledge, to be able to use it in different conditions. In creative games, a wide Way opens up for children to fantasize, make an item, experiment.

In the game, moral qualities are also formed in connection with mental development. Experiences during the game process leave a deep mark on the child's mind, so the game helps to raise good feelings, great dreams and

aspirations, healthy interests in the child. In the game, the child learns to control his behavior, overcome difficulty, firmly stand up for his goal. The game is an independent activity, in the process of which children begin to communicate with their peers. They are united by a common goal, common experiences in walking to it. Therefore, the game plays an important role in the upbringing of friendly relations, the formation of Team life skills, organizational skills. In a small children's team united by a joint game, complex relationships arise.

The task of the educator is to involve each child in an active game, to build relationships between children that are based on friendship, truthfulness, sense of responsibility for their comrades. The game is played by children at their own discretion, but there is no strict rule that in any other activity is associated with the behavior of children, as in the game. Such a strict rule applies to both creative play and rule play, and the rule is set by the children themselves.

That is why the game makes children itizoml, teaches them to subordinate their actions and thoughts to the set goal.

The game also helps to fulfill the task of Labor Education. In their games, children reflect people of different professions, with which they do not imitate the movement of adults, but also reflect their attitude to work, to work. The game often evokes in the child the desire to work, forcing him to prepare and make the necessary things for the game. In the game there is an interest and development in the technique that is characteristic of children of the present time, children make all kinds of cars and play with technical toys.

The game is an important tool of yeststik upbringing. In the game, creative imagination, the ability to think arise and develop. A well-chosen kiss will help to educate artistic taste. The beauty and rhythm of movement in action games captivates children. The great educational importance of the game does not come true on its own. The game can be useless, even harmful, sometimes lamenting bad interests, bad feelings. In order for the educator to carry out the task of comprehensive development of children with the help of the game, it is necessary to regularly influence it.

When solving this task, the game should be connected with all aspects of educational and educational work in the children's garden. The game reflects and develops the knowledge and skills that children receive in training, through which the child is taught to life. On the second hand, the qualities brought up in the game are transferred to other types of activity.

The role of the game in the pedagogical process. The pedagogical process in the kindergarten should be organized in such a way as to create favorable

conditions for their good upbringing, taking into account the features of the growing young organism of preschool children. To do this, the leading place of the game should be occupied in the organization of children's lives. The time allotted for children's play cannot be eaten by stretching exercises or other activities on the agenda.

In the "kid" program, the daily routine includes nutrition, body training, training, as well as a game. The game begins with a small group (from the third age) as a form of Organization of children's lives.

The game starts on the ground until breakfast (15-20 minutes) and is held after breakfast, between workouts, outdoors, after sleep. it is recommended to arrange role - playing games, build-making, action (with a ball).

In the middle of the workout, action, rule games are held. They largely depend on the content of the occupation.

Outdoor games include running, shooting, games that are associated with gliding, rule games ("cunning fox", "White Poplar blue Poplar"). There will also be construction, role-playing: sports games, games played with natural materials (with sand, water, clay), didactic games, games that develop children's movement, dramatized games. The Educator Guides all the games.

Games after daytime sleep include building games, a game to put on Earth, role-playing games, didactic games, etc.

The types and content of the games require them to be organized by each age group. The game is conducted in the pedagogical process, interconnected with Labor and education, other activities of children.

In the game, children are practically mastering the surrounding reality. Children do not set the main goal of mastering knowledge in the game process, improving it, but acting as adults, getting in touch with other children, the attractiveness of game tasks, competition and the like require the child to preserve and strengthen his knowledge. Children don't even play didactic games to find out something. But in the process of the game, the child's knowledge will improve on its own, without realizing it. In the process of education (training), a specific goal is set that forms the knowledge of children. The educator informs children of new knowledge, in which the sleeve of educational activity forms simple skills. The nature and content of education affects the content of children's games and develops it.

Knowledge gained in hobbies, lessons, develops children's play activities, interests.

On the second hand, various game methods are also used in the exercises with

different techniques. Such methods make it possible to collect children's attention, activate their perception, fully assimilate knowledge.

It should also be mentioned that there is something in common and difference between work and play in the pedagogical process. Children's manual labor is directly related to the game. Especially when they go to a large group, children not only play with existing toys, but also make those they lack themselves with the help of adults from paper, yogochs, cardboard, natural materials.

The relevance of the game with Labor is that children always keep their own toys in advance.

The results of scientific research work carried out in subsequent years showed that labor activity in small groups requires the introduction of game features. It turns out that first children master how adults perform the labor process, and then reflect this in their games, and only then move on to independent labor activity. In order for children's labor to be fun, it is often carried out in a playful way. For example, when cleaning the playground, children transport garbage in their cars instead of transporting it on mattresses, making boxes of cardboard in the workshop. The fact that children reflect adult labor in their games forms respect for this labor in them. This is also an example of the fact that oyunnipg is related to Labor.

Thus, the game covers the entire life of children in a well-established pedagogical process and ensures its interesting passage.

The peculiarity of children's play is that it reflects the surrounding life, the activities, deeds, actions of people, their interaction in the work process. During the game, the room can be a sea for children, a forest, a metro station, a railway station, etc. k.

Another feature of children's play is its amateur style (private activity). This is not its external signs, but the true essence.

The creator, creator of the game is children. They reflect in the game the life events and events familiar to them in their relationship to them.

Another characteristic feature of the children's game is the mutual attachment of movement, words and images in it. In the game, the child lives with the emotions, experiences, actions of the Hero, which he is reflecting on. Therefore, often when they call her by name, she does not answer and says: "I'm not, I'm a captain." Then the tutor said: "Comrade captain, your ship will soon go out to sea. Matros should be strong and healthy. Line them up for exercise," he says. Then the captain, happy with savlat, gives the team: "line up for Physical Education."

The child never plays quietly, even if he plays one himself, he speaks with a toy, communicates with the hero he is describing, his mother, patient, doctor so everyone - instead of everyone-speaks for himself. The word helps the image to open up better.

Speech yega very great importance in the game process. Children with speech accompaniment exchange ideas, share their feelings and experiences. The word helps to establish friendly relations between children, to treat the events and facts of life around them in the same way.

In the game, the image, the action of the game, the word are interconnected and form the main basis of the activity of the game, serve as a means of reflecting being.

Coming from the game created by the children themselves, yoka is the Goya of the game proposed by adults, the content, the game actions, the roles, the rules of the game are the edges that make up its structure.

The Goya of the game is to determine what to play: "shop", "hospital", "pilots", "Mother-Child" ("Family"), "kindergarten" and the like. Depending on the content of the game, the Goya, such games of their children can be divided into several specific groups:

- A) games that reflect household marriages ("family", "kindergarten", "hospital"
- b) games reflecting the creative work of people (metro construction, peasant labor, construction of houses, enterprises, etc. k.);
- C) games that reflect social events, traditions (holidays, demonstrations, travel; waiting for guests.

This kind of games is of course conditional, and it is also possible that different life events will be reflected in one game. Goya is the content, living texture of the game, which determines its development, game behavior, the variety and interconnection of children's relationships.

The fun of the game and how children participate in it depends on the content of the game. The role that the child plays in the game's the main core and structural feature of the game. That is why these games received the name role-playing or plot-role-playing games. Depending on the role that the child gets, he goes into the same image and believes in his truthfulness.

In short, music psychology is such a branch of psychology that covers such an issue as children's palpable perception, musical hearing of music, the limits of the sense of hearing, hissing the lad, rhythmic of music, tactile perception of the word, memorization, execution and restraint from it. Children's musical talent

and intelligence amaze and fascinate us with their endless possibilities, miraculous nature.

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